

A Cursory View on Women in Constituent Assembly

Dr. Vanthangpui Khobung, Assistant Professor, Department of Education in Social Sciences,
National Institute of Education, NCERT, New Delhi-110016.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0274-9010>

Dr. Savita Sagar, Assistant Professor, Department of Education in Social Sciences,
National Institute of Education, NCERT, New Delhi-110016.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-6351-0215>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14704596

Abstract

This paper explores the critical yet often discounted role of women in India's Constituent Assembly, which laid the foundation for its democratic governance. Despite the inclusion of 15 women members—such as Sarojini Naidu and Vijay Laxmi Pandit—historical narratives frequently neglect their contributions, focusing more on their male counterparts. The study highlights these women's diverse backgrounds and their multifaceted engagements in areas like freedom fighting, law, reform, and politics. It sought to fill the gap in constitutional history by showcasing their significant roles in legislative processes and social causes, advocating for gender diversity in nation-building. By raising awareness about their contributions and the issues they championed during the Assembly debates, the paper seeks to inspire contemporary readers to appreciate the importance of women's participation in society and to motivate them towards active involvement in national development.

Keywords: Women, Constituent Assembly, Participation, Contributions

Background

The role and status of women in society is a prominent subject in academic discourse and debate, as reflected in numerous scholarly works and literature. The universal recognition of the importance of women's political participation for societal progress and overall development is particularly evident in the foundational phase of modern India, notably during the establishment of India's democratic political system by the Constituent Assembly. The Constituent Assembly of India not only framed the Constitution but also played a pivotal role in shaping the democratic governance of the newly independent nation. The idea for a Constituent Assembly was first put forward by M.N. Roy in 1934 and later adopted by the Indian National Congress (Austin, 2018). The British Cabinet Mission of 1946 subsequently recommended the establishment of the Constituent Assembly. Initially comprising 389 members, including representatives from British India and the princely states, the Assembly's membership was later reduced to 299 after partition. Notably, it included 15 women members who actively participated in the deliberations alongside their male counterparts. They were Ammu Swaminathan, Annie Mascarene, Begum Qudsiya Aizaz Rasul, Dakshayani Velayudan, Durgabai Deshmukh, Hansa Jivraj Mehta, Kamala Chaudhry, Leela Roy, Purnima Banerji, Renuka Ray, Sarojini Naidu, Sucheta Kriplani, and Vijay Laxmi Pandit. Their contributions to nation-building were remarkable and inspiring. They came from diverse backgrounds, encompassing experiences as freedom fighters, lawyers, reformists, suffragettes, and politicians. However, the literature on constitutional history and mainstream historical narratives often overlooks the detailed stories of these women, focusing more on other prominent members. This paper aims to address this gap and highlight the life and

contribution of women members of the August Assembly for an inclusive historical record. These women members had multifaceted personal lives, displaying commitment not only as members of the Assembly, but also to various social causes, literature, education, and diplomacy. The paper aims to raise awareness about the historical significance of women's roles in legislative processes, highlight the issues raised by these women members during the Constituent Assembly debates, and provide engaging discourse on their contributions to social causes, literature, education, and diplomacy. It seeks to foster a sense of pride and motivation among readers, encouraging them to actively participate in the nation's growth. Furthermore, it aims to inspire readers to appreciate the importance of gender diversity in nation-building activities.

Ammu Swaminathan

Fondly called Ammukutty, Ammu Swaminathan, was born in the in Palghat (Palakkad) district of Kerala on 22nd April 1894. Ammu never went to school and received only a rudimentary education at home. When Ammu was 13, her mother arranged an alliance for her which conformed to the *Sambandam* system with Subbarama Swaminathan, a Kerala Iyer Brahmin. The couple registered their marriage in England because the *Sambandam* traditions of the Nair caste state that women cannot inherit property after marriage. Ammu's marriage was a watershed moment in her life, and it changed the trajectory of her life, laying the foundation for her future in Politics and as a Social Reformer.

Ammu became interested in Mahatma Gandhi's life and work as a result of her husband's influence. In 1917, she formed the Women's India Association along with other prominent women. In 1934, she joined the Indian National Congress which at that time was strongly advocating for universal adult franchise and equal constitutional rights for women and this reflected in her activities as part of the Indian National Congress as well. She was an active participant in the Quit India Movement and as an aftermath was jailed for a year in Vellore. In 1946, she was elected to the Constituent Assembly from Madras and was one of the very few women involved in the drafting of the Indian Constitution. Ammu was also a strong advocate of pro-women legislation and pushed for the Sarda Act or the Child Marriage Restraint Act, the Age of Consent Act and the various Hindu Code Bills aiming to reform succession, inheritance and marriage laws. Later as a member of the Lok Sabha she also pushed for maternity benefits for women. Ammu had faced caste discrimination in her marital life as she belonged to a caste considered lower in the hierarchy than her husband, who was a Brahmin. This was her lived experience that she used to push for change towards equality and dignity for all.

In the Constituent Assembly, she supported the inclusion of freedom of speech, association and worship in the Fundamental Rights as she felt that there would be no mistake about it and nobody can say that our Constitution did not include freedom of worship to every citizen of this country. She insisted that the Constitution makers needed to understand that constitutions are historically “gendered” and remain so; their provisions often have a disparate or differential impact on women, even where they appear gender-neutral. She drew the attention towards “gender auditing” of constitutions with a simple focus on equality rights and examines constitutional language, interpretation, structures and distribution of power, rules of citizenship, processes of representation, and the constitutional recognition of international and customary law. Its discussion of rights treats equality rights and reproductive rights as distinct issues for constitutional design. This could ensure that the Constitution provides for gender equality and inclusivity in the real sense, and not just on

paper. In 1959, she became the Vice President of the Federation of Film Societies. Later she also headed the CBFC and the Bharat Scouts and Guides. A dynamic personality and strong woman, Ammu Swaminathan remains an inspiration to us even today. Dabbling in multiple areas that women at that time had restricted access to and excelling in all of them, she not only led the struggle for independence but also empowerment and gender equality.

Annie Mascarene

Annie Mascarene was born on 6th June 1902 in Trivandrum/ Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, to a Latin Catholic family. She obtained a double M.A. in history and economics in 1925 and went on to become a lecturer in Ceylon, present Sri Lanka. Later, she decided to return to India and acquired a law degree. She again returned to teaching at her alma mater-Maharaja's Colleges for Arts and Law, Trivandrum (Jani, 2018). She occupied inspiring positions as a few women legislators of her time at different levels and platforms. Her involvement and contribution in the national movement, Travancore State Congress (STC), Travancore-Cochin State Assembly, Constituent Assembly and ultimately in the first Lok Sabha frames her political career as a prominent public figure during the freedom struggle, women architect of the Constitution of India and one of the first women legislator in independent India. She was one of the three women members of the Travancore State Congress way back in 1938. She served on the Economic Development Board of the Travancore government in 1938 and 1939 and as a member of the committee to look into the Hindu Code Bill. She was a member of the Travancore-Cochin Legislative Assembly between 1948 and 1952 where she served briefly as Minister in charge of Health and Power. She also occupied a prominent position as one of the few women members in the Constituent Assembly.

One distinguished contribution of Annie Mascarene was as a member of the Constituent Assembly. Her speeches in the Constituent Assembly included various topics for discussion. She also addressed the criticism that the Constitution is too centralized and may undermine state autonomy. On the Federal Framework, she specified strongly upon the form of government and sharing of power between the centre and state. She underlined the significance of centralization, but that it should be done later in the democratic process rather than at the start when it can appear dictatorial or authoritarian (Scaria, 2016). Annie was firm on her position regarding provincial autonomy and independence of election (Reeja, 2018). According to her, elections in the province needed to take place independently without any influence from the centre. Annie wanted Travancore to be included in Indian territory for which she played a convincing role. In this process, she acknowledged what Sardar Patel did by uniting all the princely states together part by part and by avoiding any greater violent clashes anywhere. Presence of Annie's idea on federalism can be found in the Constitution of India through various provisions although it has not been directly written.

She was elected as a Member of Parliament (MP) from Trivandrum/ Thiruvananthapuram in 1952 and earned a distinguished position in the history of Kerala as its first women MP in independent India. Annie's will to work for togetherness and India's unity helped to integrate the nation. Travancore-Cochin boundaries were redrawn after independence and brought together to get the present-day state namely Kerala in 1956. Mascarene's contribution towards the provincial election and the idea of federalism remains crucial. It can be noted that her thoughts on centralization were considered by the drafting committee and necessary changes were made in Article 289 of the draft Constitution.

Begum Qudsia Aizaz Rasul

Begum Qudsia Aizaz Rasul was born in 1909 in Lahore (then part of India) and was educated at the Convent of Jesus and Mary, Shimla. She graduated from Queen's Mary College of Lahore. Her Father Zulfikar Ali Khan was the Nawab (ruler) of Maler Kotla (now in Punjab) and her mother Mahrunnisa was the daughter of the Loharu estate. Begum Qudsia was married to Nawab Aizaz Rasul of Sandila state (Hardoi). Begum Qudsia Aizaz Rasul had a dynamic personality and excellent oratory skills combined with Knowledge and wisdom enabled her to debate the socio-economic, political and educational challenges of her times. As her political experiences increased, she established her political legacy and developed her political career. Since 1927, she has been an active member of the All India Women's Conference. In 1937, she was elected as a member of UP Legislative Council, at the age of just 28 years. She contested from an un-reserved seat which was not easy to win. From 1937-40 she held the post of Deputy President of the UP Legislative Council. In 1946, she was elected as a member of the Constituent Assembly.

As a member of the Constituent Assembly, Begum Qudsia Aizaz Rasul spoke frequently on various subjects. Mrs. Rasul had a brilliant vision of justice, equality, and fraternity. Her belief in the best interests and ideals of a democratic state was unshaken. She participated in the Constituent Assembly debates not as a women member but on all issues relevant to India's integrity, development and prosperity of all Indians without any discrimination. Her political orientation and higher modern education carved her personality into a true leader and activist and broadened her vision of human rights and human development. These were the main characteristics of her commitment towards nation-building. Participating in a debate at the assembly on Fundamental Rights, Mrs. Rasul emphasised the need to develop a mechanism to protect these rights. The concept of institution-making and developing them was a priority for her to protect the rights of the people in an independent state. She was also firm about the continuation and stabilization of the Fundamental Rights in the Constitution to be adopted. She opposed reservation for minorities in Legislative Assemblies as she believed in the composite culture of India. Therefore, she didn't favour the idea of partitioning India into two states. She also criticized the 'Zamindari' system which she considered was against the common mass's welfare and was exploitative in nature.

In 1950, she dissolved the Muslim League party and joined the Congress Party. From 1950-52, she was a leader of the opposition in the UP assembly. From 1952-56, she was a member of the Rajya Sabha. In 1953, she was appointed as president of All India Women's Hockey Federation (retained the post till 1972). The Indian Women Hockey Cup was named in her honour due to her keen interest in the promotion of hockey among Indian women. In 1953 and then in 1955, she became the Prime Minister's Good Will delegate to Japan and Turkey respectively. She was elected to the UP Legislative Assembly four times: 1969, 1974, 1980 and 1985. From 1969-71, she was the Minister of Social Welfare and Minority Affairs in the UP government.

Dakshayani Velayudhan

Dakshayani Velayudhan was born on 15th July 1912 in Mulavukad, a small island in what is now the Ernakulam district of Kerala. Her father was a schoolteacher and she belonged to the *Pulaya* community; a group subjected to severe oppression under the caste system. She began school at the age of six and, with the support of a scholarship from the Cochin State Government, became the first Dalit woman in India to graduate. She earned her

B.Sc. in Chemistry and later obtained a teacher's training certificate in 1938. Dakshayani began her career as a teacher.

In 1913, the *Kayal Sammelanam* (the Backwater Conference), played a pivotal role in shaping Dakshayani's commitment to fighting caste oppression. Hundreds of *Pulayas*, including her family members, gathered on small boats in Kerala's backwaters because they were barred from assembling on land. This event had a profound impact on Dakshayani, who later requested that her biography be titled *The Sea Has No Caste*. Her experience of discrimination as a Dalit teacher further pushed her to reconsider her career in education. Seeking justice for her community, she urged the Cochin government to allow her to serve in the legislature. When her request was granted, she resigned from teaching and was nominated to the Cochin Legislative Council in 1945. Subsequently, the Cochin government nominated her to the Constituent Assembly, where she played a key role in shaping India's Constitution.

As the only Dalit woman in the Assembly, her presence was a powerful statement against the entrenched caste system. She argued for the inclusion of Harijans in the Hindu representation in Muslim-majority provinces and urged that Harijans be given the same representation rights as other Hindus, emphasizing their integral place within the broader Hindu community. She expressed strong support for clause 11 of the Fundamental Rights report, which addressed the exploitation of marginalized communities. She linked the economic exploitation of the Harijans to their social disabilities. She saw an Independent United India as being more beneficial to the abolishment of caste rather than a measured divvying of electoral politics. She opposed separate electorates or reservations for Harijans, arguing that these mechanisms would not lead to genuine representation. She cautioned that such systems could result in candidates being purchased by others and not truly representing the Harijan community. She criticized the Draft Constitution for being too similar to the Government of India Act of 1935 and argued that India needed more decentralization. She spoke passionately about the issue of untouchability and remarked that we cannot expect a constitution without a clause relating to untouchability. She urged that untouchability be eradicated not just through laws but through continuous social reform and education. She passed away in 1978, but her tireless efforts for Dalit rights continue to inspire activists today. Her advocacy extended to broader social reforms, including education for Dalit women and protections for their labour rights. Through her work, she helped lay the foundation for a more just and equal society. In 1977, she founded the Mahila Jagriti Parishad in Delhi, championing women's rights. Her lasting impact is acknowledged by the Kerala Government through the Dakshayani Velayudhan Award, instituted in 2019 to honour women empowering others.

Durgabai Deshmukh

G. Durgabai was born on 15th July 1909, in Rajahmundri, Kakinada. She was involved in the Indian freedom movement from a very young age: at 12, she quit school to protest the imposition of English as the medium of education. At the age of 14, she volunteered at a conference held by the Indian National Congress in Kakinada (constitutionofIndia.net). She later started the *Balika Hindi Paathshala* in Rajamundry to promote Hindi education for girls (amritmahotsav.nic.in). In May 1930, she participated in the Salt Satyagraha in Madras and was imprisoned in 1930 and 1932. In prison, she studied English and completed her M.A. from Andhra University. She went on to study law at Madras University and practised at the Madras Bar for a few years (constitutionofIndia.net). "She had chosen to study law to help women, having had intimate interactions with women

convicts as a political prisoner at Vellore” (Chetan, 2022). In 1936, she established Andhra Mahila Sabha to coach young Telugu girls in Madras for their Matriculation examination conducted by the Banaras Hindu University. Durgabai founded and edited a Telugu journal called Andhra Mahila (constitutionofIndia.net). She had a brilliant legal practice when she came to the constituent assembly (Chetan, 2022). In the assembly, she was also a member of the steering committee and was entrusted with the task of moving most of the 700 proposed amendments (Chetan, 2022). She had spoken on various dimensions in the assembly. With a strong legal knowledge, she discussed the appointment of judges in provincial high courts, the establishment of high courts in newly created provinces, the appellate jurisdiction of the Supreme Court and also the role of the Supreme Court as the guardian of the constitution. Her other constitutional topics included constitutional remedies for fundamental rights, the neutrality of the Governor, limitations on individual freedom and other democratic credentials. She also raised several social issues such as the prohibition of the Devadasi system, the opening up of Hindu religious and educational institutions for all sections and the protection of children and youth from exploitation and abandonment. Also, Durgabai insisted on making Hindustani the national language instead of Hindi (Rajya Sabha Secretariat, 2012).

After the constitution was framed, she contested the Lok Sabha elections of 1952, but she lost. Then, she became a member of the first Planning Commission. She had also established the Central Social Welfare Board. In these roles, she addressed the relationship between the state and its machinery as well as between the state and civil society (Chetan, 2022). In 1958, she headed the National Committee on Girls' and Women's Education. Durgabai was awarded the Nehru Literary Award in 1971 for her contribution to the promotion of literacy in India. She was awarded the Padma Vibhushan in 1975. The Central Social Welfare Board instituted a yearly award in her name to recognize voluntary organisations for outstanding contributions to women's welfare and empowerment (constitutionofIndia.net). She passed away on 9th May 1981.

Hansa Mehta

Hansa Mehta was born on 3rd July 1897 in Surat, Gujarat in a Brahmin family. Mehta graduated in philosophy from Baroda College in 1918. Then, she went to England to study Journalism and Sociology. She also read literature by herself. When she was in London, she met other prominent women like Rajkumari Amrit Kaur and Sarojini Naidu. In 1924, Hansa Mehta married Jivraj Mehta, who was of a caste lower than Hansa and thus, they had to face resentment within the family as well as society. After returning from England, Mehta undertook diverse roles and began working in many directions. She served as the president of *Bhagini Sabha*, established the *Desh Sevikas* in 1932, participated in many freedom movements, and was jailed several times. She was one of the founding members of the All-India Women's Conference (AIWC) and also, later served as its President in 1946. In the same year, Mehta, along with Renuka Ray and Kamala Devi Chattopadhyay, framed the 'Indian Women's Charter of Rights and Duties' which called for equal status and opportunity for women, equal pay, suffrage and equal rights in matters of marriage and divorce. She stood for the Bombay Legislative Council seat in the provincial elections of 1937 and won. She served as the principal secretary and remained in the council till 1949. After Independence, she was elected to the constituent assembly. As she had to divide her time between her role as a member of the constituent assembly and as a delegate to the UN during the framing of the constitution, she spoke on only three occasions in the assembly. In the assembly, Mehta proudly supported the Objectives Resolution for the equality of opportunity it mentioned

along with the equality of status, which, in her opinion would be very beneficial for the women. In her final speech on the draft constitution motion moved by Ambedkar, Mehta spoke on a range of issues – working of the constitution, minorities, untouchability, purdah, prohibition and common civil code. Also, she presented the National Flag on behalf of the women of India. At the international level, Hansa Mehta represented India as a delegate to the United Nations. In 1946, she was a part of the United Nations sub-commission on the status of women. In 1947, she was one of the only two women to be a part of the United Nations Commission for Human Rights. She was the one who modified one word in Article 1 of the historic Universal Declaration of Human Rights from “all men are born free and equal” to “all human beings are born free and equal” (www.un.org).

An important committee having her name was popularly known as the Hansa Mehta Committee. This was constituted by the National Council for Women's Education in 1962. The committee proposed common curricula for both boys and girls up to the primary stage. It recommended core curricula of Home Science for both sexes at the middle stage and the inclusion of crafts or handiwork or productive labour on the general courses at the secondary level. She was vice chancellor of the S.N.D.T. Women's University from 1946 to 1948 and vice-chancellor of the University of Baroda from 1949 to 1958. At Baroda, she was the first woman to hold that title at an Indian co-ed university (New York Times, 2024). In 1959, for her distinguished service, Hansa Mehta was awarded the Padma Bhushan.

Kamala Chaudhary

Kamala Chaudhary was born in 1908 in a progressive family in Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh. She was well-educated, which was relatively rare for women of her time, and her upbringing exposed her to the ideas of social reform and the importance of education. She pursued higher education and was known for her intellectual and progressive outlook. While making serious efforts at the socio-political and cultural level to improve the living standards of women, she also became actively involved in the Indian independence movement, influenced by Mahatma Gandhi and the Indian National Congress. She was closely associated with Mahatma Gandhi and took part in the Civil Disobedience Movement in 1930. Inspired by Gandhi's non-violent call for freedom movement, she formed Charkha Committees to unite women. She was particularly engaged in mobilizing women for the cause of freedom, encouraging them to participate in non-violent protests and civil disobedience movements. Her activism led to her arrest on several occasions during the British colonial rule.

Choudhry was elected as a member of the Constituent Assembly of India, which was responsible for drafting the Indian Constitution from 1946 to 1950. Although there were only 15 women out of 299 members, Kamala Chaudhary was one of the few women who played a critical role in advocating for gender equality and social justice. She worked closely with other prominent women leaders like Hansa Mehta, Rajkumari Amrit Kaur, and Sarojini Naidu, and contributed to discussions on fundamental rights and the Directive Principles of State Policy. Kamala Chaudhary's role in the Constituent Assembly was marked by her advocacy for social justice and women's rights. She was a strong proponent of gender equality and worked towards ensuring that the Constitution reflected these principles. Her contributions were not limited to women's issues; she also addressed broader social concerns, including the rights of marginalized communities. Chaudhary's speeches and interventions were grounded in the Indian knowledge system, drawing from traditional values while advocating for progressive change.

After India gained independence in 1947, Chaudhary continued her work in the areas of rural development and women's education. She was particularly interested in the upliftment of rural women and worked to promote sustainable livelihoods through education, skill development, and self-help initiatives. She was involved in several social welfare programs and initiatives aimed at poverty alleviation and community development. Kamala Chaudhary is also remembered for her involvement in the establishment of the IIM Ahmedabad in 1961. She played a significant role in shaping the institute's early policies, curriculum, and approach to management education. Kamala Choudhry's life and work exemplify the spirit of service and commitment to social justice. Her contributions remain significant in the history of modern India, particularly in the context of women's participation in politics and governance. Choudhry passed away in 1970, leaving behind a legacy of courage, activism, and reform. She is remembered as a pioneering woman leader who helped lay the foundation for a more inclusive and democratic India.

Leela Roy

Leela Roy was born on 2nd October 1900 in Assam. She was educated privately at home and later she was sent to primary school in Assam at Eden High School. She did her graduation from Bethune College Calcutta and received the Padmavati Gold Medal in English. She fought her way through to get admission at the University of Dhaka which was meant only for male students and became the first woman to earn a master's degree from the university. While studying at Dhaka, she became the assistant secretary of the All-Bengal Association which was formed to organize support in favour of women's right to vote. This is one of her biggest contributions to women's suffrage in India. As early as just 23 years old she established a women's organization named *Deepali Chatra Sangha*. One of the main achievements of this organization was the establishment of primary and high schools for girls and centres for teaching handicrafts for girls from economically deprived sections of society and martial arts to develop self-defence. In 1926 she joined *Sri Sanga*, an all-male revolutionary group fighting for India's independence. With her help, many women joined the *Sangha*. Later she set up the *Mahila Atma Raksha* Fund where women were taught self-defence and martial arts. Leela Roy made a new venture in 1930 with the publication of *Jayasri*, the first magazine edited managed and wholly contributed by woman writers. She broke the stereotype by keeping *Jayasri* away from typical housewifely matters like household tips, cooking, sewing, knitting and so on and keeping its focus on socio-political issues. The same year she took an active participation in the anti-salt movement in Dhaka. She was arrested along with her associates as a mark of protest against the salt tax. The Bengal Provincial Congress women's organization was founded by her. Influenced by her capacity and ability Subhash Chandra Bose made her a member of the women's subcommittee of the National Planning Committee. When he formed the Forward Bloc, she became a member of the central executive body in 1940. Leela went to Noah Khali in Bengal now in Bangladesh and set up relief camps for families affected by the riots. She walked around the region covering over 140 kilometres in six days rescuing hundreds of people. In the same year, she was elected to the Constituent Assembly from Bengal. She was elected to the Constituent Assembly from Bengal on 9th December 1946. She was the only woman from undivided Bengal to be elected to the constituent assembly. However, she resigned a few months later in protest of the partition of India.

Even after resigning from the constituent assembly as a mark of protest Leela Roy continued to contribute to the social and political causes of the country. As a result of the

partition and her resignation from the Constituent Assembly, she moved ahead and formed the women's organization named *Jatiyo Mohila Shangha* in West Bengal. When the Forward Bloc was divided in 1949, she became the general secretary of the West Bengal Forward Bloc. When the Forward Bloc merged with the Praja Socialist Party in 1954, she became one of the national executive members and in 1960 became chairman of the party. Although she gave up active politics, she continued to guide her old comrades. Leela Roy breathed her last on 11th June 1970 after a prolonged illness.

Malati Choudhury

Malati Choudhury was born on 26th July 1904 in a Bengali Brahmin family. Malati's family was rich with politicians but she did not choose the path of formal politics. Instead, she decided "to work for and with the people". She was immensely influenced by Tagore and got the chance to acquire knowledge directly from Rabindranath Tagore at *Shantiniketan*. In *Shantiniketan*, Malati not only obtained a degree but also acquired huge knowledge in various types of art and culture. She married Nabakrushna Choudhury in 1927. She joined the national movement as a teenage girl. Through her efforts, hundreds of women came out of their houses and took an active part in the Salt Satyagraha. Malati and Nabakrushna helped poor farmers to improve sugarcane cultivation. They also started adult education in the surrounding villages. In 1933, Malati and her husband organised the *Utkal Congress Socialist Workers League* which rallied against Casteism and untouchability. It later became the Orissa branch of the *All-India Congress Socialist Party*. The *Prajamandal* movement broke out in 1938 under her initiative and leadership of Nabakrushna. Malati, along with others addressed the people and advised them to carry on peaceful and non-violent agitation and to open negotiation with state authorities (amritmahotsav.nic.in). In 1934, she became an important figure in Gandhi's *padayatra* in Orissa. She accompanied Acharya Vinoba Bhave during the Bhoodan Movement and joined Gandhiji during his Noakhali visit. Malati sold all her ornaments to publish the weekly magazine of the League, *Sarathi* that talked about the conditions of farmers under the Britishers. In 1940 she became the President of the Provincial Congress Committee and in 1942 she joined as a member of the All-India Congress Committee. In 1942, she participated in the Quit India movement for which she was sentenced to three years imprisonment. She had also come to be known as "Joan of Arc" in such struggles.

Malati Devi was elected to the Constituent Assembly in 1946 from Odisha through a Congress ticket. However, she resigned from the Assembly that very year to work with Gandhi because she felt "unfit" for the work. She wanted to continue working on the ground with farmers, Dalits, tribals and children. In 1946, Malati set up the *Bajiraut Chhatravas* which aimed to educate the children of freedom fighters scheduled castes, scheduled tribes, other backward classes and underprivileged sections of society. In the same year, Malati also founded the *Post Basic School*. In 1948, Malati, along with some other freedom fighters, set up the *Utkal Navjeevan Mandal* in Orissa which worked for rural development and tribal welfare in Orissa. All of this gave her the tag of 'mother of Odisha'. She began a series of measures to aid in rural development. This included adult education and women and children empowerment programmes. As an underground leader, she guided the progress of the movement in different parts of Odisha. Even after independence, she continued to be active in social life and fiercely opposed the emergency imposed by Prime Minister Indira Gandhi. She received the national award for child welfare (1987), the *Utkal Seva Saman* (1994), and *The Tagore Literacy Award* (1995). She died on 15th March 1998 at the age of 93.

Purnima Banerji

Purnima Banerji was born in 1911 in Kalka, Punjab. She was the younger sister of the renowned freedom fighter Aruna Asaf Ali, whose guidance inspired her to work towards uniting rural communities for the cause of independence. Remarkably, Purnima appeared for her graduation exams while in jail. Her political journey began when she became the Secretary of the Indian National Congress Committee in Allahabad. She actively joined the freedom struggle alongside prominent leaders. As a member of the Congress Socialist Party, Purnima organized trade unions, and Kisan meetings, and worked tirelessly for rural communities. She played an active role in major national movements, including the Salt March and the Quit India Movement. In the year, 1930, she took part in the civil disobedience movement against British rule. She along with Sucheta Kriplani took part in the satyagraha movement in 1942. Later, both of them were put behind the bar.

In the Constituent Assembly, she contributed to discussions on various topics. She opposed the idea of schools providing religious instruction and forcing students to adopt specific beliefs. She advocated for a curriculum that would encourage young minds to explore the world and think openly, rather than promoting exclusivity or division. Furthermore, she argued that a secular state should not interfere with individual religious beliefs but should ensure that education remains neutral, inclusive, and respectful of all perspectives. She emphasized the critical role of the Upper House in maintaining a balanced and representative democracy. She highlighted how discussions in the Rajya Sabha allow for multiple voices from different states and Union Territories to be heard, including representatives from diverse fields. This diversity helps ensure that legislation reflects a wide range of perspectives. Banerjee argued for lowering the minimum age for Rajya Sabha members as it would encourage more young people to participate in politics, bringing fresh ideas and energy to the legislative process. She emphasized the importance of debating financial and local bills, as these are key to shaping financial policies and resource allocation in the country. She believed that local bills should focus on addressing the needs of marginalized communities and ensuring equitable distribution of resources. According to her, panchayats and local bodies can only function effectively if they have a steady flow of finances. She advocated for legislation that would encourage the establishment of industries in villages and local areas, helping boost local economies. She favoured a progressive taxation system, where higher taxes are levied on those with higher incomes and lower taxes on those with lower incomes, to promote fairness and reduce economic inequality. She suggested that the Government should possess control over important resources to provide security and save it from falling into the hands of foreign enterprises. Purnima Banerji was a bold lady and would protest or raise her voice against any wrongdoing. Her love for education is evident from the fact that she appeared for the B.A. examination from the jail itself. By her melodious voice, she led the chorus of the national song 'Jana Gana Mana' in the Constituent Assembly. Unfortunately, she passed away in 1951 due to ill health in Nainital.

Rajkumari Amrit Kaur

Rajkumari Amrit Kaur was born on 2nd February 1889 in Kapurthala Royal Family, Punjab. After an initial period of home-schooling, she was sent to Sherborne School in Dorsetshire, England to complete her school education. She continued her stay in England, graduating with a remarkable academic and extra-curricular record from the University of Oxford. Once she completed her education, Kaur returned to India aged 20. Though she

belonged to a royal family, she was deeply influenced by the teachings of Mahatma Gandhi and actively participated in India's independence movement. In the initial years after her return, Kaur committed most of her energy to social causes concerning women such as abolishing the practice of purdah, child marriage and the Devadasi tradition. By 1927 she had co-founded the All-India Woman's Conference, serving as its secretary in 1930 and president in 1933.

Rajkumari Amrit Kaur was not only one of the few women in the Assembly, but she also played a crucial role in the drafting process. One of her key contributions was advocating for equality before the law (Article 14) and non-discrimination based on sex (Article 15). These provisions were groundbreaking as they guaranteed that no person, regardless of their gender, would be treated unfairly under the law. She believed that women's empowerment was essential for the progress of a nation, and she worked tirelessly to ensure these principles were reflected in the Constitution. During debates, she argued passionately for women's right to education, employment, and protection from social evils like child marriage. Her work, along with other pioneering women, laid the foundation for the legal and social reforms that would follow in independent India. Education and health remained the main focus of her work for the next several years. She was the Deputy Leader of the Indian delegation to UNESCO in 1945 and 1946. After independence, Rajkumari Amrit Kaur became India's first Health Minister, continuing her fight for women's rights. In 1950, Rajkumari Amrit Kaur was elected the first woman President of the World Health Assembly. She also campaigned to eliminate diseases like malaria and tuberculosis, which were rampant at the time, and to improve sanitation and clean water supply across rural India. She was also a founder-member and Chairperson of the Indian Red Cross Society. She later became the vice-president of the International Red Cross Society. She also held the post of President at the Indian Leprosy Association and the Tuberculosis Association. She was among the Board of Trustees of the Nankana Sahib Education Trust and the *Hindustani Talimi Sangh*. She was one of the founding members of Delhi's Lady Irwin College. Her work towards the welfare of children led to the founding of the Indian Council of Child Welfare, serving as its first President from 1948 to 1958. In 1956 Princeton University conferred her with an honorary Doctor of Laws degree. Kaur passed away on 6 February 1964 at the age of 75 in New Delhi. She was a voice for women and the underprivileged, ensuring that their needs were not ignored in the nation's foundational document.

Renuka Ray

Renuka Ray was born on 4 January 1904, in Calcutta, Bengal Presidency into a distinguished family. As a young girl, Renuka lived for a while in London and went to Kensington High School, then did her B.Sc. from the London School of Economics. She had teachers like Harold Laski, William Beveridge, Clement Atlee, Eileen Power and others. She met Gandhi at the age of 16 and this had a profound effect on her. She married Satyendranath Roy at the age of 25. When Renuka Ray completed her studies in London and returned to India, she joined the AIWC in 1932. In 1934, as the Legal Secretary of the AIWC, she submitted a document titled 'Legal Disabilities of Women in India; A Plea for a Commission of Enquiry'. Her document showed their commitment to legal review of the situation of women before the Law in India. Renuka argued for a uniform personal law code, arguing that the position of Indian women was one of the most iniquitous in the world. In 1943 she was nominated to Central Legislative Assembly. At the request of the International Alliance of Women, she drafted the Memorandum submitted on behalf of Indian women to the League of

Nations. She was the only woman in the Central Assembly to represent women's views on the Hindu Code Bill from 1943 to 1945. Renuka Ray was elected to the Constituent Assembly in July 1947. As an Assembly member, she strongly supported women's, children's and marginalized section's rights. Ray dedicated her efforts to combat women's trafficking and enhancing the working conditions of female labourers. Taking a firm stance against the reservation of seats for women, she emphasised that such measures undermine women's capabilities and potential. Ray emphasized on elimination of gender-based discrimination, and the establishment of particular rights for women in the workplace. She strongly raised her voice against religious intervention or instruction in the education system. Renuka Ray stated that India as a whole nation, is not divided into minority and majority. She suggested multiple constituencies with cumulative voting to ensure the representation of minorities and others without making a separatist tendency. On centre-state discussion, she advocated that provincial autonomy is important, but central supervision in education and health is crucial for nation-building. She suggested that Linguistic realignment should be postponed for ten years to allow tensions to settle. Also, she said prioritizing education in mother tongues is important, but maintaining national unity and strength is more critical.

In May 1949, Ray became a member of the United Nations delegation from India. As an Indian representative, she stood up, not just for India, but her voice echoed the stance of all non-aligned countries as well. She introduced the 'Relief-Through-Work' scheme for women in the flood-affected *Sundarbans*(Ray, 1982). She became the minister of Relief and Rehabilitation in the West Bengal Government. She decided to contest the Lok Sabha elections in 1957 and won. Her main objective to become a parliamentarian was to take effective measures for the rehabilitation of the refugees from East Bengal (Ray, 1982). She chaired a committee on *Social Welfare and Welfare of backward classes* in 1959. She passed away in 1997 at the age of 93, leaving a commendable legacy behind.

Sarojini Naidu

Sarojini Naidu was born on February 13, 1879, in Hyderabad, India, to a Bengali Brahmin family. Her original name is Sarojini Chattopadhyay. At the age of twelve, she wrote a play, "Maher Muneer" which impressed the Nizam of Hyderabad. The ruler was so captivated by her work that he offered her a scholarship to pursue her education abroad. At the age of 16, she went to England to study at King's College, London, and later at Girton College, Cambridge. Her time in England not only shaped her intellect but also exposed her to progressive ideas of feminism, nationalism, and equality. She also met prominent figures like Arthur Symons and Edmund Gosse, who encouraged her to focus on writing poetry about India. Her entry into the political sphere was greatly influenced by the partition of Bengal in 1905. Naidu soon became involved in the Indian freedom struggle. In 1916, she met Mahatma Gandhi and became a key follower of Gandhi's principles of non-violence and Satyagraha. She actively participated in the Non-Cooperation Movement (1920), the Civil Disobedience Movement (1930), and the Quit India Movement (1942). Naidu's ability to mobilize people with her stirring speeches made her one of the most effective leaders in the Indian National Congress. In 1925, Sarojini Naidu became the first Indian woman to preside over the Indian National Congress. This was a historic moment, not only for her but for the women's movement in India. During her political career, Sarojini Naidu faced multiple imprisonments. She was jailed alongside other prominent leaders for participating in Gandhi-led movements against British rule. After India gained independence in 1947, Sarojini Naidu was appointed as a member of the Constituent Assembly that drafted the Constitution of

India. Naidu's contribution to the Assembly was significant, especially in advocating for the inclusion of women's rights and the protection of minorities. She pushed for equal rights and opportunities for women under the new Constitution. Naidu also focused on ensuring that India's Constitution embraced a vision of inclusivity and justice for all sections of society, particularly women and marginalized groups. In the Constituent Assembly, her focus was on ensuring equality, particularly for women. She strongly advocated for the inclusion of fundamental rights and worked towards ensuring that women had equal representation and opportunities in the new India. Her advocacy contributed significantly to the inclusion of provisions for women's rights in the Constitution.

Sarojini Naidu was known as the "Nightingale of India" for her lyrical and evocative poetry. She was deeply inspired by Indian themes, nature, and the struggle for freedom. Her writing combined romanticism with patriotism, and she was known for her eloquent speeches and essays as well. In 1947, Sarojini Naidu was appointed as the Governor of the United Provinces (present-day Uttar Pradesh), becoming the first woman to hold the office of a state governor in independent India. Her tenure as governor was marked by her efforts to uplift rural women and improve education and healthcare in the state. She passed away on March 2, 1949, while still in office as the governor of the United Provinces.

Sucheta Kripalani

Sucheta Kripalani was born on 25th June 1908 in Ambala, Haryana in a Bengali Brahmo family. She graduated from one of the prestigious colleges of Delhi University; Indraprastha College. Kripalani became a lecturer at Banaras Hindu University and taught Constitutional History till 1939. She married Acharya Kripalani in 1936, a Congress party member and a prominent freedom fighter. Kripalani joined the Indian National Congress in 1938 and actively participated in the freedom movement. She served as the Secretary, for one and half years, to the Foreign Department and Women's Section of the Congress. She was committed to the Indian Independence movement she moved to Allahabad from Banaras to take charge as the Secretary in the Women's section. She was the founder of the All India Mahila Congress. She participated in the Satyagraha movement due to which she was imprisoned in 1940 and she was at the forefront for her active involvement in the 'Quit India movement' She was arrested in 1944 and she was imprisoned for a year.

Sucheta Kripalani was elected in 1946 to the Constituent Assembly from the Kanpur constituency of the United Provinces which is largely today's Uttar Pradesh. She was a part of the sub-committee that drafted the Indian Constitution. Thereafter she became a member of the Flag Presentation Committee that presented the first Indian Flag before the Constituent Assembly. On 14th August 1947 at midnight, she sang 'Vande Mataram' in the Independence Session of the Constituent Assembly. She worked dedicatedly with Mahatma Gandhi in the partition riots. All these involvements moulded her to become a prominent politician in the new Independent India. Sucheta Kripalani became the first ever woman Chief Minister in India by becoming the CM of Uttar Pradesh. She served from 2nd October 1963 to 13th, 1967. She was elected to the Lok Sabha in 1952, 1957, and 1962 and served as cabinet minister in 1962. She served as Lok Sabha MP till 1971. At a later point, she and her husband parted ways in political affiliation and joined different parties but this did not let Sucheta leave any of her roles. She retired from politics in 1971 and she died in 1974.

Vijaya Lakshmi Pandit

Vijaya Lakshmi Pandit was born on 18 August 1900, in Allahabad (now Prayagraj) into a prominent and politically influential family. Like many women from wealthy and

influential families in early 20th-century India, she received her education at home under private tutors. Her early education included learning English, Hindi, and other subjects essential for a well-rounded upbringing. In 1921, Vijay Lakshmi married Ranjit Sitaram Pandit, who was also involved in the Indian nationalist movement and was a staunch supporter of Indian independence. During the early 1930s, she became actively involved in the Non-Cooperation Movement led by Mahatma Gandhi. She was imprisoned in 1932 during the Civil Disobedience Movement where she protested against the British salt tax and other oppressive colonial laws. Vijay Lakshmi was a key participant in the Quit India Movement, which resulted in her imprisonment. She was the first Indian woman to hold a cabinet post, a decade before independence in 1937. She had the honour to move the first resolution after the inauguration of Provincial Autonomy in the United Provinces to demand a Constituent Assembly to draw up a constitution for an independent India. Vijaya Lakshmi Pandit played a significant role in the AIWC, serving as an active member and later as its president from 1940 to 1942 (Scaria & Nigam, 2016).

Vijay Lakshmi Pandit was a strong advocate for women's rights during her time in the Constituent Assembly. She played a significant role in debates surrounding the idea of equality before the law and the prohibition of discrimination on grounds of religion, race, caste, sex, or place of birth. She believed that the government had a responsibility to provide its citizens with access to quality education and healthcare, especially for women and children. She supported measures to ensure that historically oppressed communities would have access to education, employment, and representation. She was actively involved in the discussions surrounding the inclusion of Fundamental Rights in the Indian Constitution, advocating for the protection of civil liberties and individual freedoms. She supported the creation of democratic institutions in the Constitution, including a parliamentary system that would ensure the separation of powers and checks and balances necessary for a functioning democracy. She supported the distribution of powers between the central and state governments, recognizing the diversity of India's regions, languages, and cultures. She also contributed to discussions on the structure of the executive branch, particularly concerning the role of the Governor. She advocated for a foreign policy rooted in non-alignment, peaceful coexistence, and international cooperation. As newly independent India's top diplomat, she served as ambassador to the Soviet Union, the United States, Mexico, Ireland and Spain and high commissioner to the (Basu, 2013). Life and Thought of Vijaya Lakshmi Pandit, 2019). In 1953, Vijay Lakshmi Pandit made history as the first woman elected President of the United Nations General Assembly. After her illustrious diplomatic career, Vijay Lakshmi Pandit returned to domestic politics making significant contributions to Indian politics and social reform. From 1962 to 1964, she served as the Governor of Maharashtra. In addition to her political and diplomatic career, Vijay Lakshmi Pandit was a prolific writer and public intellectual. She passed away on 1st December 1990.

Conclusion

The brief sketches of the lives of the women in the Constituent Assembly illustrate their challenging journeys, serving as an enduring source of inspiration. Their roles were hard-earned, resulting from lifelong struggles against various obstacles, including gender, caste, and class. Despite the patriarchal norms dominating historic India, each woman carved out her own space. Their determination to confront injustices and advocate for essential rights defined their contributions, ensuring that women in independent India would have a better journey. Each of these fifteen women made unique contributions, striving for significant

change. They truly were the founding mothers of the Indian Constitution, shaping the rights and freedoms we enjoy today.

References

- [1] Austin, Granville. (2018) *The Indian Constitution: Cornerstone of a Nation*. Oxford University Press, New Delhi.
- [2] Basu, T. (2013) *The life and times of Vijaya Lakshmi Pandit*. Vikas Publishing House, New Delhi.
- [3] Constitution of India. www.constitutionofindia.net.
- [4] Chetan, Achyut. (2022) *Founding Mothers of the Indian Republic: Gender Politics of the Framing of the Constitution*. Cambridge publication.
- [5] Choudhury, Janmenjay (2012) "Role of Malati Choudhury and her associates in the Indian National Movement." *Odisha review*.
- [6] Home Department Political (1), File No.3/44/43, 1943, The National Archives of India. New Delhi.
- [7] Jani, S. (2018, August 6) *Annie Mascarene: A trailblazer from Travancore. Feminism in India*. <https://feminisminindia.com/2018/08/06/annie-mascarene-trailblazer-travancore>
- [8] National Archives of India. (n.d.). *Vijaya Lakshmi Pandit: Trailblazer of Indian diplomacy*. <https://www.nationalarchivesofindia.gov.in>
- [9] Rajya Sabha Secretariat. (n.d.). *Selected speeches of women members of the Constituent Assembly*. Rajya Sabha. <https://cms.rajyasabha.nic.in>
- [10] R, Reeya. (2018) *Women and freedom movement in Travancore: Re-imagining the role of Annie Mascarene* (Doctoral dissertation), University of Kerala. <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/560283>
- [11] Rangarajan R., "On political representation of women | Explained." <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/on-political-representation-of-women-explained/article68415532>
- [12] Ray, Renuka. (1982) *My Reminiscences: Social Development During Gandhian Era and After*. Allied Publishers Private Limited.
- [13] Scaria, A. M., & Nigam, S. (2016) *The Founding Mothers: 15 Women Architects of the Indian Constitution*. Media House.
- [14] *Selected Speeches of Women members of the Constituent Assembly*. Digital Sansad, New Delhi.
- [15] Singh, G. N. (1941) "The Idea of an Indian Constituent Assembly." *The Indian Journal of Political Science*, 2(3), 255-272. Indian Political Science Association.

Author Contribution Statement: NIL

Author Acknowledgement: Nil

Author Declaration: I declare that there is no competing interest in the content and authorship of this scholarly work.

The content of the article is licensed under [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) International License.